

Major Themes in Nissim Ezekiel's Select Poetry

by **T. Saheeda Begum**, *Guest Lecturer,*
Department of Humanities,

Dr. B.R. Ambedkar Institute of Technology, Port Blair - 744103

&

Naw Jennifer, *Guest Lecturer,*
Department of English,

M.G. Govt. College, Mayabunder - 744204

Introduction :

Poetry is a form of literature that uses aesthetic and rhythmic qualities of a particular language such as phonaesthetics, sound, symbolism and meter - to evoke meanings in addition to, or in place of, the prosaic ostensible meaning. Poetry has a long history, dating back to the Sumerian Epic of Gilgamesh. Nissim Ezekiel, a widely recognized poet of India has started writing his verse in this world language. He is one of the major poets in the modern Post-World War II phase of Indo - Anglian poetry. To him poetry is not a gift to be adorned but a craft to be studied seriously. He believes in the revision of a poem and works hard on it, till it achieves a kind of perfection.

He writes poetry to understand and organize his own self as well as the total self of humanity. To do this he has to be elementary without taking down. His personal life also fits with these kinds of need. He is a Jew, born in India. He has spent most of his life and growth in abroad. His language is English, his environment is Indian. His religious background is Jewish and his city is Bombay, which with its

complexity and further troubles him to his total living. This confusion in his existential identities and the tension due to that confusion enable him to see the dichotomies of modern Indian life. Vasant A. Shahane says:

There is clearly a very close connection between Ezekiel's life and his poetic work. He is primarily a poet seeking, sometimes successfully, a balance between an almost involvement with life and an intellectual quest for commitment. His poetry emerges from a tension between opposites, an emotional plunge into life and a spiritual abstraction out of that world; a craving for a prayer and a temptation for irony; a passion for this world and a hankering of the world beyond.

Ezekiel deserves all the praise showered on him by A.N. Dwivedi when he says that Ezekiel's unflinching devotion to the muse has gained for him historical significance and that "as a poet Ezekiel is aware of his cultural milieu and native (that is Indian) problems. His sharp sensibility enables him to grapple with the situations around him without nostalgically recalling his stay in England or dreaming of a foreign land. He gives careful thought to his ideas, medium of expression and form of words and phrases and does not attempt to depict what is gaudy and inane and mere adolescent."

His ideal in '*A Time to Change*' is a curious mixture of being a good poet and having a fairly conventional life, the refrain sings but reads a bit like parody - 'To own a singing voice and a talking voice, / A bit of land, a woman and a child or two'. For someone who was soon to be the voice of urban discontent, Ezekiel's notion of the good life seems rather naïve:

He has to build something with able hands
And knowing eyes, with some instruction
From his parents, ancestors and friends,
Altered slightly here and there to suit his strength.

In *The Third* (1958), written between 1954 and 1958, many of the poems concern love, marriage, the discontent of marriage, affairs pursued or failed to be pursued outside marriage, memories and fantasies of other loves. While it would be foolish to translate the poems directly into real life - after all Ezekiel remained married - and to forget that poets create personae who live their imaginings and conflicts, Ezekiel's poetry from *The Third* onwards will often be concerned with the conflicts of marriage, new romances, and the delights of new loves.

Through the poem 'Island', Ezekiel clearly points out the rapid growth or development of the city Bombay. On the first scale of meaning, the poet describes the picture of the metropolitan city, Bombay. In this city, the poet observes, there is neither song nor sense, because all the people in the city were busy with their jobs and their household works. So the poet Ezekiel has to do something for the people in the well developing city.

Ezekiel gives importance to the relationship between the speaker and the listeners are basically Indian. The poet's conception of the Indian prototype in the poems, "The Professor," "The Patriot," and "Goodbye Party of Miss Pushpa T.S." could be verified, as we go along, from authoritative sources external to the poems.

Ezekiel's another poem "Enterprise" which is appeared in the fourth volume. Through this poem Ezekiel himself said that most of his poems were written for his personal, therapeutic purposes, in this poem a situation is examined with ironic detachment in the hope that it would offer the writer with a realization of his pent-up feelings. This poem is about a group of men, including, the poet set out on a pilgrimage. Through this poem we can understand how the Indians give importance to their religion, and their spiritual journeys.

We stood it very well, I thought,
Observed and put down copious notes
On things the peasants sold and bought.
The way of serpents and of goats,
Three cities where a sage had taught.

Through the poem 'The Railway Clerk', Ezekiel clearly pointed out the main problems faced by the middle class family people. In this poem the protagonist is Railway Clerk who is interested, and sincere in all of his work, but he has annoyed of his boss, for neglecting his leave form two times. He wants to take rest of his continuous work, he has tired both physically and mentally, therefore he wants to take leave for a couple of days, even though he works regularly, the fan upon his table was not repaired for last two months.

My desk is too small
the fan is not repaired for two months.

'The Night of the Scorpion' is a very fine example of 'unified sensibility.' The poet realistically presents the incident of an Indian village woman stung by a scorpion in a rainy night. The poem is suffused with the realistic portrayals of superstitions of rural villages. It also contains, the motherly love for the child and the helplessness and a lack of education among the poor peasants of the Indian villages.

The poem opens with a prosaic, dry and monotonous language:

I remember the night my mother
was stung by a scorpion. Ten hours
of steady rain had driven him
to crawl beneath a sack of rice.

Conclusion :

Through this one can understand, Ezekiel's interest and his thirst on Indian culture, especially, his importance on the Indian youths' basic problems, the urban people's life and their blind believes, their strong belief in God etc.

His language, style, rhythm and simplicity in his poetry. The disparity between what one has learnt to expect from the Standard English and what one finds manifest in the "Indian English" here has thus become a great creative opportunity to the poet to light up some aspects of the common Indian personality.

References :

- Ezekiel, Nissim : Collected Poems 1952-1988, New Delhi: Oxford University Press, 1989, Print.
- Awasthi, Mandavi : "Alienation and Belongingness in the Poetry of Nissim Ezekiel and A.K. Ramanujan: A Comparative Study," Seeds in Spring, Contemporary Indian English Poetry, Drama, & Critics. Ed. O.P. Budholia, New Delhi: Adhyayan Publishers, 2008, 78-88.